

Microbial Assessment of Some Selected Ready-To-Eat Food Samples in Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria

Olusegun-Awosika, Bukunmi Damilola

Department of Biology, Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo

Corresponding author's email: b.d.olusegunawosika@gmail.com, 09034430986

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18164436>

Abstract

The consumption of ready-to-eat foods, commonly referred to as fast food, is currently the most convenient feeding pattern in Nigeria. This study aims to assess the microbiological status of some selected ready-to-eat food samples, including fried rice, jollof rice, meat pie, and sausage roll, in a selected fast-food outlet in Akure, Ondo state, Nigeria. Microbial analyses of the food samples were carried out, and jollof rice had the highest average total bacterial count, at 7.8×10^4 cfu/ml, and a fungal count of 2.0×10^4 sfu/ml. The biochemically identified bacteria from this sample are of *Bacillus* sp., *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Corynebacterium* sp., which are likely to cause different diseases in the human body. The fried rice, baked meat pie dough, and its fillings and baked sausage roll dough show moderate bacterial growth of 5.0, 5.2, 3.8, and $3.2 (\times 10^4)$ cfu/ml, respectively, with fungal growth of 2.0, 1.8, 3.5, and $3.0 (\times 10^4)$ sfu/ml, respectively. The sausage roll filling has the lowest average bacteria and fungi counts of 2.0×10^4 cfu/ml and 1.6×10^4 sfu/ml. Seven bacterial isolates were identified with their % occurrence as *Staphylococcus aureus* 30%, *Bacillus* sp. 17.4%, *Corynebacterium* sp. 17.4 %, *Micrococcus* sp. 13%, *Aerobacter aerogenes* 8.7%, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* 8.7% and *Proteus vulgaris* 4.3%. *Aspergillus niger* predominated the fungal isolates with 75% occurrence, and *Fusarium oxysporium* with 25 % respectively. Therefore, a hygienically prepared and packaged food must retain the best quality required for consumers' acceptability and safety.

Keywords: Fast food, Food Safety, Ready to eat, Food samples

INTRODUCTION

The busy life schedule has opened a gap for ready-to-eat outlets to thrive in business. Food-borne diseases and problems related to the sanitary and microbiological quality of foods continue to be of major interest and concern in Nigeria and other countries in the world. Foods referred to as ready-to-eat (fast foods) are prepared and consumed at eateries without further preparation (Rane, 2011). The consumption of ready-to-eat foods has been reported to be associated with serious health problems (Adams and Moss, 2000; FDA, 2000). WHO (2000) reported that foodborne illnesses of microbial origin are a major health problem associated with street foods as well as fast food centers, and this is as a result of the traditional processing methods that are used in preparation, inappropriate holding temperature, and poor personal hygiene of food handlers, which are major points of contamination. Fast foods are frequently associated with diarrhea diseases,

which occur due to improper additives, the presence of pathogenic bacteria, environmental contaminants, disregard for good manufacturing practices (GMPs), and good hygiene practices (GHPs). Bhowmik (2010) reported that vendors are poorly educated, unlicensed, and untrained in food hygiene. This study was designed to determine the sanitary quality of commercially sold food at retail outlets in Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria. As fried rice, jollof rice, meat pie, and sausage roll are the very popular forms of ready-to-eat food among the general public, a need to ensure food safety is necessary.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Sample collection: four samples (fried rice, jollof rice. Meat pie and sausage roll) of freshly prepared ready to eat foods were purchased from a standard eatery. The jollof and fried rice was collected in sterile transparent plates used for food packaging while the sausage roll and meat pie were collected in sterile paper bag. The samples were brought to the laboratory for further analysis.

Culture media: the culture media (nutrient agar, MacConkey agar and potatoes dextrose agar) used were prepared according to the Manufacturers' standard. The pour plate method was carried out according to the method of Collins and Lyne (2004). The serial dilution was carried out by aseptically measuring 1g of the food samples into 9.0 ml of cooled sterilized distilled water, thoroughly shaken to ensure even dislodgement and distribution. Exactly 1 ml of the dilution factor 10^4 and 10^6 were inoculated into sterilized Petri dishes for culturing

Enumeration of Microbial Colonies: the microbial colony was counted with the aid of a colony counter. Calculation of colony forming unit (CFU) per ml and spore forming unit (SFU) per ml for the fungi growth was calculated as:

CFU/ml or SFU/ml = number of colonies × dilution factor ÷ ml of sample suspended

Characterization of the microbial isolates: the bacteria and fungi colonies were morphologically observed considering the shape, size, pigment, elevation and marginal characteristics and biochemically identified with varying biochemical tests. The fungi isolates was microscopically examined after staining the smear with two drops of lacto-phenol-in cotton blue dye under the light microscope.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Microbial colony count of bacteria and fungi

From the food samples analysed, the average total bacteria count in cfu/ml and fungi count in sfu/ml of each food samples are shown in Table 1. The results of total bacteria count ranged from 2.0×10^4 to 7.8×10^4 cfu/ml. The highest bacteria count was noticed in jollof rice and the least in sausage roll fillings. The average total fungi count ranges from 1.6×10^4 to 3.5×10^4 sfu/ml which was highest in meat pie fillings, and the lowest count was observed in sausage roll fillings.

Table 1: Average total bacteria and fungi colony count in the selected food samples

Samples	Food Samples	Bacterial (cfu/ml)	Fungal (sfu/ml)
Sample A	Fried Rice	5.0×10^4	2.0×10^4
Sample B	Jollof Rice	7.8×10^4	2.2×10^4
Sample C	Baked meat pie dough	5.2×10^4	1.8×10^4
Sample D	Meat pie fillings	3.8×10^4	3.5×10^4
Sample E	Baked sausage roll dough	3.2×10^4	3.0×10^4
Sample F	Sausage roll fillings	2.0×10^4	1.6×10^4

Each figure is an average of values from two replicates.

Morphological and Physiological Characteristics of Isolated Bacterial and Fungal

The physiological characteristics of the seven (7) bacteria isolated from the food samples show a colonial morphology predominance of circular, convex colonies with entire edges, but also demonstrate noticeable diversity in colour, shape, margin, and elevation, indicating the presence of multiple microbial species.

Table 2 shows the morphological and physiological characteristics of the five (5) isolated fungal species in the food samples.

Table 2: Morphological and Physiological characteristics of fungi isolated from the food samples

Isolates	Morphological characteristics	Physiological characteristics	Probable organisms
A	White, fluffy, and woolly	Non-septate	<i>Fusarium oxysporium</i>
B	Dirty green, raised and fluffy	Non-septate	<i>Aspergillus butyricum</i>
C	Black, umbrella-like mycelium Shape	No conidia, conidiospore hangs the spore at the top	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>
D	Yellow, creamy unbranched mycelium shape	Presence of conidia with conidiospores	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>
E	Dirty, yellow, and fluffy	Non-septate	<i>Aspergillus fumigates</i>

All fungi isolated from the sampled ready-to-eat foods showed a wide trend of growth of *Aspergillus* sp. The dominating presence of *Aspergillus* species on the sampled foods could be due to its rapid sporulation, development, and relative adaptability to a wide range of environmental conditions as compared to other organisms.

The biochemical identity of isolated bacteria from the food samples is presented in Table 4. 2 (gram-negative) bacteria were isolated, with 5 (gram-positive) bacteria, respectively. They all reacted differently to the various biochemical analyses.

Table 3: Biochemical characteristics of isolated bacteria from the food samples

Isolate	G	sha	C	C	M	L	G	s	H ₂	U	Sp	Probable organisms
	ra	pe	a	o	o	a	l	u	S	r	or	
	m		t	a	t	c	u	c	for	e	e	
	re		a	g	i	t	c	r	m	a	fo	
	a		l	u	l	o	o	o	ati	s	rm	
	ct		a	l	i	s	s	s	on	e	in	
	io		s	a	t	e	e	e			g	
	n		e	s	y							
			e									

B1	+	Cocci	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	<i>Micrococcus sp.</i>
B2	+	Cocci	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
B3	+	Cocci	+	-	-	+	+	+	-	+	-	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>
B4	-	Rod	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	-	<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>
B5	+	Rod	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	<i>Corynebacterium sp.</i>
B6	+	Rod	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	<i>Bacillus sp.</i>
B7	-	Rod	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	<i>Aerobacter aerogenes</i>

Key: + = positive, - = negative,

The percentage occurrence of bacterial and fungal isolates from the food samples in this study is identified to be resident and transient strains found according to Tables 3 and 4. *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus sp.* and *Corynebacterium sp.* were the predominant organisms with 30%, 25.5% and 25.5% respectively. These are isolated mainly from fried rice, jollof rice, baked meat pie, and sausage roll. *Micrococcus sp.*, with 13% was isolated from baked sausage roll dough and its filling. *Aerobacter aerogenes* (6%) and *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (8%) are isolated from the baked meat pie and sausage as well. These are contaminations resulting from improper food handling practices. *Proteus vulgaris* 5% is isolated from the sausage roll fillings.

Aspergillus sp. predominated amongst the fungal isolates, with 75% occurrence, and *Fusarium oxysporium* with 25% occurrence, respectively. *Aspergillus sp.* was isolated from all the food samples collected, while *Fusarium oxysporium* was only isolated from baked sausage roll dough and its filling.

Figure 1: Percentage occurrence of fungi isolated from the food samples

Figure 2: Percentage occurrence of bacteria isolated from the food samples

The food samples studied were extensively processed by boiling and baking methods, resulting in varying microbial loads and presence. The two fungal species isolated, *Aspergillus sp.* and *Fusarium oxysporium*, are common moulds in soil, air, and organic matter. These are ready contaminants in foods and feeds. It was therefore not surprising that the food samples, especially meat pie fillings, were a subject of invasion. The microbial counts in the food samples were within the standards for acceptable ready-to-eat foods (KEBS, 2003). According to Oni *et al* (2004), staphylococcal food poisoning caused by enterotoxin-producing strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* was the most common foodborne illness. They suggest that the food contamination in ready-to-eat foods are mainly due to poor hygiene in peeling of raw vegetables long before consumption, and in-thorough washing of fresh vegetables and cooking utensils (Mensah *et al.*, 2002) Dierick *et al*, (2001) has also reported *Bacillus sp.*, as a well-known cause of foodborne illness that is not commonly reported due to their mild symptoms. Therefore, ready-to-eat food vendors such ensure that standard microbiological safety requirements acceptable for food production and consumption are met to ensure food safety.

CONCLUSION

It's quite unfortunate that there has been no strict application of legal standards relating to the hygiene in production, processing, packaging, and distribution of ready-to-eat food in the Akure metropolis of Ondo State. With the possibility that contaminants may also come from the environment and raw materials, food handlers should ensure that ready-to-eat foods are kept at a standard temperature by microwave oven treatment before serving, ensure standard manufacturer practices, and hygienic handling of the finished product.

REFERENCES

- Adams M. R., and Moss M. O. (2000). *Food Microbiology*. 2nd edition. Royal Society of Chemistry, Cambridge, UK.
- Bhowmik S. (2010). *Street Vendors in the Global Urban Economy*. *Routledge India*.
- Collins C. H., and Lyne P. M. (2004). *Microbiological Methods*, 8th edition. Arnold Publishers, London.
- Dierick K., Van Coillie E., and Swiecicka I. (2005). Fatal Family Outbreak of *Bacillus cereus*-Associated Food Poisoning. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology* 43(8): 4277–4279.
- FDA (2000). *Bad Bug Book: Foodborne Pathogenic Microorganisms and Natural Toxins Handbook*. U.S. Food and Drug Administration, Center for Food Safety and Applied Nutrition.
- KEBS (2003). *Microbiology of Food and Animal Feeding Stuffs – Horizontal Method for the Enumeration of Microorganisms – Colony Count Technique at 30°C*. Kenya Bureau of Standards, Nairobi.
- Mensah P., Yeboah-Manu D., Owusu-Dark K., and Ablordey, A. (2002). Street Foods in Accra, Ghana: How Safe Are They? *Bulletin of the World Health Organization* 80(7): 546–554.
- Oni M. O., Ogunbanwo S. T., and Onilude A. A. (2004). Identification of Enterotoxigenic *Staphylococcus aureus* from Some Nigerian Foods. *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition* 3(3): 172–176.
- Rane S. (2011). Street Vended Food in the Developing World: Hazard Analyses. *Indian Journal of Microbiology* 51(1): 100–106.
- World Health Organization (WHO) (2000). *Food Safety and Foodborne Illness*. Fact Sheet No. 237.